

Microfaeces Analysis and Lead Mineralization in Laminated Silty Limestone of Wunbye Formation at Hpuye-Kyaukpauk Area, near Bawsaing, Shan State (South)

Kyi Kyi Swe*

Abstract

The research area lies in Kalaw Township, north of Bawsaing, in the southern Shan State. The Wunbye Formation of Pindaya Group (middle Ordovician) is exposed in the north, north east and north-west part of Myozo village. It is composed of eight microfacies namely bioclastic packstone, peloidal bioclastic packstone, mottled dolomitized mudstone, dolomitic mudstone, calcareous siltstone, bioclastic peloidal wackestone, algal laminated mudstone, and peloidal bioclastic wackestone. On the basis of depositional environments, these microfacies are grouped into three facies associations. They are supratidal facies association, intertidal facies association and subtidal facies association. Supratidal facies association consists of mudstone facies, dolomite facies and calcareous siltstone. Intertidal facies association comprises of mudstone facies and wackestone facies. Subtidal facies association is made up of packstone facies. The major diagenetic processes are cementation, dissolution, replacement of one mineral by another, recrystallization, compaction and fracturing. The main economic and important ore minerals of this area are galena, cerussite and barite. The ore-bearing rocks belong to three stratigraphic levels in Wunbye Formation. The mineralized zones are grouped according to the respective rock units, it is observed that the laminated silty limestone of lower Wunbye rock unit is distinctive for the occurrence of galena, the middle Wunbye rock unit is noted for galena associated with barite, and the upper Wunbye rock unit is characterized for the occurrence of cerussite. The mineralization is resulted from the injection of hydrothermal ore fluids into the Ordovician rocks. So it is a stratabound deposit.

Introduction

The study area, a segment of the Bawsaing range, is situated in Kalaw Township. It is situated between latitude 20 ° 58' 00" N to 21° 03' 00" N and longitude 96 ° 45' 00" E to 96° 52' 00" E. It is demarcated by vertical grids 31 to 45 and horizontal grids 41 to 51 in one inch topographic maps are 93 C/16, 93 D/13. It lies about six miles north of Bawsaing. It can be accessible in all weather from Bawsaing by car and motorcycle (Figure 1).

Objectives

The main purposes of the study area include as follows;

- (1) To carry out petrographic analysis of Wunbye Formation
- (2) To conduct a carbonate microfacies analysis based on the resultant petrological aspects and other evidences
- (3) To focus the possible depositional environments on the basis of study of carbonate facies and their facies associations

To reconstruct the possible depositional model by using the all aspects of petrological studies, carbonate facies analysis, and geometries of depositional packages in accordance with sediment production and accommodation.

* Dr., Lecturer, Department of Geology, Dagon University

Figure 1. Location and accessibility of the study area

Materials and Methods

The detailed measurement of the section was carried out from Wunbye Formation for detailed microfacies analysis. While measuring the section, lithologic features, sedimentary structures, nature of bedding, and thickness of beds are recorded. Moreover, samples were collected from the measured section.

For detailed petrographic studies, thin sections were made from the representative samples and examined under a binocular microscope.

A quantitative technique of visual estimation was applied to describe the composition by their relative abundance. Petrographic classification used in this study is adopted from Dunham (1962) and Folk (1959).

Distribution and Lithology of Wunbye Formation

The Wunbye Formation is chiefly exposed along the Okpa chaung, and in the environs of Nyaunggaing village, Shwegu village, Hpuye village and Ywahaung village (Figure 2). The physiography of this formation is mountainous unit and the height between 4500 ft and 5000 ft (Figure 3). The Wunbye Formation is made up of light to dark grey, thin to thick bedded limestone, dolomitic limestone, calcareous siltstone, algal laminated limestone, mottled limestone, pelletal limestone and bioclastic limestone. The recognizable primary sedimentary structures are small scale cross lamination, parallel laminaion, wavy continuous and discontinuous lamination.

Petrography of Wunbye Formation

Based on the view of lithology, primary and secondary sedimentary structures, biological characteristics, the Wunbye Formation can be divided into eight microfacies (Figure 4). They are (1) bioclastic packstone, (2) peloidal bioclastic packstone, (3) mottled dolomitized mudstone (4) dolomitic mudstone, (5) calcareous siltstone (6) bioclastic peloidal wackestone, (7) algal laminated mudstone and (8) peloidal bioclastic wackestone. Petrographic classification used in the present study is adopted from Limestone Classification of Dunham (1962). The microfacies descriptions and interpretations are as follows.

Figure 2. Distribution of Wunbye Formation

Figure 3. Physiography of the study area

Microfacies I Bioclastic Packstone

Microfacies Description

This microfacies occupies 10% of the measured section. They are dark grey to bluish grey color. In some exposures, parallel laminations and trough cross laminations are recognized (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Stratigraphic section of Wunbye Formation from loc. 21° 00' 49''N to 21° 00' 40''N

Petrographically, it is composed of 48% allochem, 38% orthochem, and the rest are the other carbonate grains. Allochem grains which include bioclasts and pellets. Most of the bioclasts are broken fragments. The common bioclasts are echinoids and mollusks. Most of the mollusks is filled with coarse grained sparry calcite and some filled with medium grained clear

calcite. The rest fragments are full up fine grained calcite. The periphery portion of some bioclastic grains are rimmed by micrite layer resulted as micritic envelopes. Some crinoids plates are bored by microbial organism and thick micrite layer coated with them. These carbonate grains have various sizes and display poorly sorted. Recrystallized sparry calcite occurs as intergranular cement (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Parallel lamination in the lower part of photo and upper part showing trough cross lamination (black arrow) in bioclastic packstone generally fluctuated current action in subtidal environment, loc: 21° 01' N, 96° 50.019' E, facing 120°

Figure 6. Echinoderm plates are bored by organisms and then deposited carbonate mud on it (in center of the photograph), mollusks shell fragments are filled with blocky calcite by replacement and rimmed by micritic envelopes (left below) formed by low energy oxygenated water, some grains are irregular shape, filled with micrite, and lacking internal structures which may be peloids (upper and below left), under PPL

Microfacies Interpretation

Owing to the extensive occurrence of bioclasts and cement with sparry calcite this microfacies accumulated in adequate water circulation condition. The occurrence of boring features indicates that the setting gets sufficiently oxygen and micritic envelopes show that they laid down in low energy condition, current velocity is very low condition, subtidal environment.

Microfacies II Peloidal Bioclastic Packstone

Microfacies Description

This microfacies occupies 59.3% of the measured section. They are dark grey to bluish grey color. The wavy discontinuous lamination and parallel lamination is present (Figure 7).

Petrographically, it comprises of 61% of allochem, 18 % of sparite. Most of the allochem grains are pellets and peloids, a few are bioclasts. Peloids are the important constituent of shallow marine carbonate sediments. The shapes of pellets are subrounded, ellipsoidal to irregular and their sizes are more or less equal. They show moderately sorting. They are fecal in origin, produced by deposit- feeding animals. Intrestitial pore space between pellets is filled with sparry calcite and shows loosely packing (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Wavy discontinuous lamination (white arrow) and planar contact in thick bedded limestone seen on vertical surface developed by wave action, loc. 21°01' N, 96°50.019' E, facing 120°

Figure 8. Loosely packed, moderately sorted, subrounded to ovoid ellipsoidal shape pellets are the result of syndepositional lithification, then followed by relatively early sparry calcite cementation in order to prevent compaction of these grains, under PPL

Microfacies Interpretation

This microfacies is characterized by the abundance of allochem grains, fecal pellets which show that the environment is agitated condition. These are accumulated in low energy current, subtidal environment because of the presence of parallel lamination. The preservation of recognizable pellets in limestone is clear evidence of early lithification (Wright, 1990).

Microfacies III Mottled Dolomitized Mudstone

Microfacies Description

This microfacies takes 5.3 % of the measured section. It is thick to medium bedded, light grey to grey on weathered surface while yellowish grey on fresh surface. On the bedding plane, vertical and horizontal patches filled with yellow silt are scattered throughout the bluish grey fine grained groundmass exhibit mottled structures (Figure 9).

Petrographically, it is composed of allochems, orthochems, dolomites and terrigenous detritus. Bioclasts contain 2 to 7 % of the total rock volume. 5 to 10 % of peloids are embedded in matrix. 20 to 30 % fine grained carbonate mud occur as matrix. 10 % of sparry calcite occurs as filling materials in bioclasts. Dolomite is the abundant mineral. It occupies 40-50% of the total volume. It is found in burrow structure and fine grained euhedral to subhedral dolomite crystals (Figure 10).

Microfacies Interpretation

In this mudstone, the carbonate mud was precipitated by biochemically. Formation of dolomites in the burrow mottles are the intense evaporation of sea water during the end of bioturbation. This fact indicates that they are standard microfacies belt 8, supratidal environment of restricted platforms (Wilson, 1975)

Figure 9. Mottled structures in dolomitic limestone which are seen on vertical surface resulting swirled burrow pattern (black arrow), loc. 21° 01' N , 96°50.019'E, facing 120 °

Figure 10. Burrow structure, textural contrast between burrow fill and surrounding sediment, dolomitized burrow fills (A), undolomitized host rock (B), pelecypod shell fragment (C) occurring beside burrow showing selective replacement and evaporation of marine water immediately happen at the end of bioturbation, under PPL

Microfacies IV Dolomitic Mudstone

Microfacies Description

This microfacies occupies 6% of the measured section. This rock shows light grey to grey on weathered surface while yellowish grey on fresh surface. Algal mats occur in most exposures. On the vertical surface, rib and furrow structures are found. Due to the interbedded nature of algal limestones and dolomitic limestones, the well bedded dolomitic limestones are exposed more boldly with conspicuous trend, while the less resistant beds occur only as individual blocks without conspicuous trend (Ohn Myint, 1980). The type of algal mats is laterally linked hemispheroids (LLH-S) (Figure 11).

Under the microscopic study, it contains 7 % of bioclasts, 20-40 % of orthochem and 60- 70 % of dolomite. Bioclasts are broken unidentified fragments. Micrite is mainly orthochem and occur as matrix. Sparite occurs as patches which are resulted from the enlargement of micrite (aggrading porphyroid neomorphism) and filling materials in bioclasts. Anhedral to subhedral dolomite crystals are scattered in micrite groundmass. Some dolomites show cloudy center (Figure 12).

Microfacies Interpretation

The rocks of this microfacies are rich in micrite and medium grained dolomite. The cloudy center dolomite is formed by dolomitization of micrite on low intertidal ponds .The presence of dolomites signified that sea water is rich in magnesium.

Figure 11. Algal mats are seen on cliff surface, which shows the low intertidal flat environment, S_1 surface showing (black arrow) formed by thrusting, loc. $21^{\circ} 01' N, 96^{\circ} 50.019'E$, facing 120°

Figure 12. Dolomite front (arrow) observed in the lower part of stylolitic seam separator, anhedronal to subhedronal dolomite aggregates (A) embedded in micrite matrix, source of magnesium is stylolite, which cause the selective dolomitization, under PPL

Microfacies V Calcareous Siltstone

Microfacies Description

It displays light yellow to yellow in color on both weathered and fresh surface. It occupies 2.25 % of the measure section. They are wavy, parallel thinly laminated, well jointed and indurated siltstone.

Under microscopic study, it is composed of quartz silt, mica and cemented with calcareous materials. The amount of quartz varies from 30 to 40 percents of the total volume. They are angular to subangular and moderately sorted. Muscovite mica flakes are randomly scattered.

Microfacies Interpretation

It probably damped in the quite water condition because of the presence of parallel lamination. The high content of quartz signifies that the source area not far away from the land.

Microfacies VI Bioclastic Peloidal Wackestone

Microfacies Description

This facies occupies 3 % of the measured section. It is light grey to dark grey in color. It is well compact and poorly to massive in bedding nature. Brachiopod shell fragments and other unidentified shell fragments are observed on the bedding plane. In some places, horizontal and vertical burrows are commonly observed (Figure 13).

Under microscopic examination, this rock is made up of 40 % of bioclasts, 10 % of peloids, 18% of sparry calcite, 30 % of fine-grained calcite and 2 % of dolomite. Bioclasts contain echinoderm plates and mollusks shell fragments. They are lost in primary features and filled with redeposit sparry calcite. They have no micrite coating. They are filled with single calcite plate show cleavage. Ellipsoidal shape pellets are generally oriented. The bioclasts and peloids are set in fine grained calcite. Sparry calcite occurs in voids. Hypidotopic to idotopic dolomite mosaics are set in micrite groundmass (Figure 14).

Figure 13. Photograph of many shell fragments observed on bedding plane which representing the good water circulation environments, low intertidal setting, loc. $21^{\circ} 01.016' N$ $96^{\circ} 50.024' E$, facing 120°

Figure 14. Photomicrograph of pelecypod shells filling with sparry calcite precipitation in mold of organisms after dissolution of original material, dolomite mineral are set in groundmass in the centre of photo, under PPL

Microfacies Interpretation

Texturally, poorly sorted, randomly oriented bioclasts and large amount of micrite and pellets, these sediments are accumulated under relatively quiet water environment. Due to the absence of micrite envelope, they are formed in upper intertidal environment; the current energy is moderately high.

Microfacies VII Algal Laminated Mudstone

Microfacies Description

This microfacies occupies 13.5 % of the measured section. It shows light yellow to yellow in colour on both weathered and fresh surfaces. Algal structures are the prominent features of this facies (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Photomicrograph showing the alignment of ellipsoidal shape pellets, under PPL

Petrographically, it is made up of 10 % bioclasts, 20 % micrite, 25% dolomite and the rest are terrigenous detritus. Sand to silt size quartz is the chief constituent minerals of this

rock. The algal fragments (LLH-S) are set in micrite. The groundmass micrite partially changed into rhomb shaped dolomite by selective dolomitization processes (Figure 16).

Microfacies Interpretation

The diagnostic feature of this facies is algal fragments, dolomites and micrite. These sediments are accumulated in quiet water condition, photic zone, supratidal to upper intertidal environment.

Microfacies VIII Peloidal Bioclastic Wackestone

Microfacies Description

This microfacies occupies 2.8 % of the measured section. Argillaceous seams are locally observed. It shows light grey to dark grey on weathered surface and yellowish grey in fresh surface. It is thin to thick bedded in nature (Figure17).

Under microscopic study, it is made up of 20% bioclasts, 42% of pellets and peloids, 10 % of sparite, 32 % of micrite, 2 % dolomite and 2 to 3% of fine sand size clear quartz. Pellets are subrounded to ellipsoidal shape and size range and color varies. Smaller size pellets have dark color due to high organic content while larger pellets have light brown color. Fine grained carbonate mud cemented the pellets .Sparry calcite cement found in vein stringers. Single euhedral dolomite crystals disseminated in micrite matrix and easily observed by iron oxide rims. Anhedral quartz detritus are clear and fine sand size (Figure 18).

Figure 16. Algal laminations reflecting the intertidal-supratidal (pond) condition crenulation resulting of differential weathering of mudstone and algae, loc. 21°01.016' N , 96°50.024' E, facing 120 °

Figure 17. Photomicrograph of embedded algal fragments (A) in micrite groundmass found as L.L.H-S type, selective dolomitization (B) taking place in some places, under PPL

Microfacies Interpretation

On the occurrence of pellets and signified amount of quartz sand indicate that these sediments were deposited under moderately agitated condition, intertidal to subtidal environment. Selective dolomitization signified that the presence of magnesium in sea water. Subrounded fine sand size quartz, windblown sediments, shows that it may be the winnowing setting.

Figure 18. Argillaceous seams occur on bedding plane probably formed by pressure solution resembling wavy lamination, loc. $21^{\circ}01.016'N$, $96^{\circ}50.024'E$, facing 120°

Figure 19. Two types of pellets are recognized according to their size and color. On the left of photo, dark color, smaller size pellets which may be fecal pellets and light brown color larger size peloids on the right of photo, notably quartz silt, subrounded to rounded shape and windblown sediments, under PPL

Microfacies associations and Depositional environments

Microfacies of the Wunbye Formation in the study area fall in three different facies associations. They are

- (a) Supratidal - facies association
- (b) Intertidal - facies association
- (c) Subtidal - facies association

Recognition of patterns of facies can be on the basis of visual inspection of graphic sedimentary logs or by using a statistical approach to determining the order in which facies occur in a succession, such as a Markov Analysis. This technique requires drawing a dendrogram for facies association. Facies succession shows up as higher than average transition from one facies to another see in (Figure 20). The variable amount of petrographic constituents of three facies associations are plotted (Figure 21). The possible depositional model of Wunbye Formation is derived from microfacies analysis (Figure 22).

(a) Supratidal-facies association

This facies association consists mainly of MF-3 mottled dolomitized mudstone, MF-4 dolomitic mudstone, MF- 5 calcareous siltstone and MF-6 algal laminated mudstone. The diagnostic features are large amount of microcrystalline carbonate mud, and high dolomite content.

(b) Intertidal-facies association

This facies association is made up of MF-3 mottled dolomitized mudstone, MF- 7 bioclastic peloidal wackestone, and MF- 8 peloidal bioclastic wackestone. The distinctive features of this association are mottled burrows, stromatolite structures, more dolomite content and micritic envelopes.

Figure 20. Carbonate dendrogram from the microfacies, entire upper and lower contacts among microfacies. The carbonate dendrogram depicts three distinct clusters and facies variation related to subtidal, intertidal, supratidal depositional environments. The first cluster A indicates supratidal-facies association, the second cluster B shows subtidal-facies association. The third cluster shows intertidal to subtidal facies. These three clusters indicate gradation from supratidal to subtidal facies assemblages.

(c) Subtidal-facies association

MF-1 bioclastic packstone, and MF-2 peloidal bioclastic packstone fall in this association. This environment is characterized by small amount of intraclasts, and large amount of bioclasts.

Diagenesis of Wunbye Formation

Diagenesis encompasses any physical or chemical changes in sediments or sedimentary rocks that occur after deposition. Diagenesis, thus begin at the sea floor (syngenetic or eogenetic alteration), continue through deep burial (mesogenetic alteration), and extend to subsequent uplift (telogenetic alteration) (Scholle, 2003).

The major diagenetic processes are cementation, dissolution, replacement of one mineral by another, recrystallization or strain recrystallization, physical or 152rinoids152y compaction, chemical compaction, and fracturing.

Cementation is the filling of open pore space, of primary or secondary origin, with newly precipitated materials (Scholle, 2003). The principal cement types of the Wunbye Formation in the study area are syntaxial rim cement, granular cement and blocky calcite cement.

Dissolution is the leaching of unstable minerals forming secondary pores, vugs, or caverns (Scholle, 2003). The rock was deposited below water table. Water entering from the vadose zone may be strongly undersaturated with respect to CaCO_3 originally, but as it moves down through the fresh water phreatic zone, it will become more and more saturated. Thus, at the top of the zone is an area where both calcite and aragonite are dissolved (Longman, 1981).

It is replaced of one polymorph of a mineral by another is the replacement (Scholle, 2003). In some cases, dolomite minerals replaced the other unstable minerals, calcite under favorable condition. Dolomite fabrics were classified by Sibley and Gregg (1987) as planar (idiotopic) and non-planar (xenotopic) based on the nature of boundaries.

Figure 21. Variable amount of petrographic constituents of supratidal facies association (a), intertidal facies association (b), and subtidal facies association(c)

Figure 22. Hypothetical Block Model showing the possible depositional environments of the Wunbye Formation

The development of microspar and pseudospar is attributed to prograding neomorphic recrystallization which starts the initial stages of sediment accumulation and early diagenesis. It is known as aggrading neomorphism and the reverse process is degrading neomorphism (Folk, 1959). Micrite changed into spar by sparitization in MF-5, bioclastic peloidal wackestone. It is observed as patches so it is porphyroid aggrading neomorphism.

Rim of crinoids plate is replaced by micrite at or just below the sediment / water interface (Adams and Mackenzie, 1994). Crinoid fragment is bored by microbial organisms and the holes are filled with micrite and progressively fill produces micritic envelope.

There are two types of compaction; physical compaction and mechanical compaction. In the assigned area, both types are noticed. Degree of compaction is poor to moderate because planar contact and concavo convex contact are present. Stylolites or solution seams are marked between the 154 crinoids plates. They are resulted from the pressure solution (Scholle, 2003).

Fractures are formed by tectonic activity, fluid expulsion and solution collapse (Scholle, 2003).

Lead Mineralization in Wunbye Formation

The ore – bearing rocks belong to three stratigraphic levels in Wunbye Formation. The mineralized zones are grouped according to the respective rock units, it is observed that the lower Wunbye rock unit is distinctive for the occurrence of galena, the middle Wunbye rock unit is noted for galena associated with barite, and the upper Wunbye rock unit is characterized for the occurrence of cerussite (Ohn Myint, 1980).

In the assigned area, the main economic mineral is galena (lead sulphide) and barite and the minor ore mineral is copper ore; azurite and malachite. The localities of work sites of the study area are shown in (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Work sites localities

Hpuye work site: Hpuye work site is located near Hpuye village (20°01'21.360" N 96°47'11.340" E). It is a recent mine site. Galena is mined from algal limestone (Lower Wunbye Formation, O₂w¹ (Ohn Myint, 1980). The limestone is trending 160 ° and medium to thick bedded. The galena content is about 35 – 52%. The average percent is 3 to 6 in raw materials.

Kyaukpauk work site: The work site lies in the east of Kyaukpauk village. It is worked out by Hein Naychi .It is not investigated. The mineralization zone is trending 340°. Galena is digging out from laminated siltstone, lower Wunbye Formation.

Shwegu work site: The deposit is situated in the north west of Shwegu. It is not investigated .The mineralization vein width is about 0.32 to 1.1 meter. The hosted rock is dolomitic limestone, lower Wunbye Formation. But not only galena but also it is associated with barite. The deposit is located in the local minor anticline, in which one limb dips 42°/15° and another limb dips 38°/301 °.

Thaungdwin work site: Thaungdwin work site situates in the east of Tadagan (Gr 370 400) .The mine site is investigated by Top Ten Star. The adit at Thaungdwin deposit was driven from the north –western slope of Bawmutaung (Ohn Myint, 1980). The galena associated with barite can be extracted from the laminated calcareous siltstone, middle Wunbye Formation. The galena content is 20%.

Ganaingtone work site: Ganaingtone work site is located about two miles, south-east of Tadagan (Gr 390402).It is carried out by G.P.S Joint Venture Co. Ltd in 2009. The content of galena is 45%.

The mineralization is resulted from the injection of hydrothermal ore fluids into the Ordovician rocks. So it is a stratabound deposit.

Figure 24. The content of galena from different localities of Wunbye Formation in the study area

Figure 25. The content of galena in different lithofacies of Wunbye Formation

Results

The study area, Hpuye-Kyaukpauk is extensively composed of Ordovician Limestone, Wunbye Formation. The limestone facies was originally made up of eight microfacies. Each microfacies displays its depositional environments and diagenetic processes. The transition from the mudstone facies to packstone facies represents a change in original sediment type which indicates that they are deposited in different conditions. Where interparticle lime mud was present, it inhibited the development of the calcite overgrowth and was available for selective leaching to form the visible porosity. The amount of porosity developed through dolomitization. Due to compaction processes, the veins and fractures were resulted in rocks. There is a suggestion that hydrothermal ore fluids were injected in these and lead mineralization was occurred.

Conclusion

The study area ,a segment of the Bawsaing range,is emplaced in Kalaw Township. It situates between latitude 20 ° 58 ' 00 " N to 21° 03 ' 00 "N and longitude 96 ° 45 ' 00 " E to 96° 52 ' 00 " E. One inch topographic map nos. are 93 C/16, 93 D/13, and embrace approximately 88.8 sq. kilometer.

Wunbye Formation is made up of light to dark grey, thin to thick bedded limestone. Several primary structures are formed in this formation such as small scale cross lamination, parallel lamination, and wavy continuous and discontinuous lamination.

They can be divided into seven lithofacies, which are calcareous siltstone, dolomite, mottled limestone, bioclastic limestone, algal limestone, pelletal limestone and oolitic limestone..Thickness varies from one section to another. The presence of small scale cross lamination, parallel lamination and wavy lamination point out the low to moderate energy. And the common occurrence of mega fossils fragments specified that they may be deposited in tidal environment. The mineralization is resulted from the injection of hydrothermal ore fluids into the Ordovician rocks.So it is a stratabound deposit.

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